

Syntheses of Some Benzofuroylcoumaran-3-Ones

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Preparation of several 2-benzofuroylcoumaran-3-ones $III_{(a-f)}$ by Baker-Venkataraman transformation of 2-(2'-benzofuroxy) ω -bromoacetophenones $II_{(a-f)}$ have been described. The ω -bromocompounds have been obtained by bromination of the corresponding acetophenones with copper(II) bromide in dry dioxan. The same coumaran-3-ones have been prepared by the cyclisation of ω -benzofuroyl- ω -bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenones $IV_{(a-f)}$ obtainable by direct bromination of the corresponding diketones with bromine in dry chloroform at 0° in the presence of potassium carbonate.

LITERATURE describing the synthesis of 2-acylcoumaranones¹⁻¹¹ is not large, although such compounds have obvious possibilities in view of the biological activities⁹ reported with this class of compounds. Indeed, to be best of our knowledge not a single instance is known where the acyl unit was obtained from an acid containing a heterocyclic ring system.

We report here the preparation of a few 2-benzofuroylcoumaran-3-ones.

The bromo intermediates $V_{(a-f)}$ under the experimental conditions will necessarily be unstable and suffer ready cyclisation to $III_{(a-f)}$.

Alternatively the 1:3 diketones $IV_{(a-f)}$ ^{1,3} were subjected to bromination in dry chloroform at 0° in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate by bromine in chloroform adopting a suitable modification of the method of Geissman and Armen⁵. The bromo compounds, however, could not be obtained in pure state as repeated crystallisation did

	$I_{(a-f)}$		$III_{(a-f)}$		$IV_{(a-f)}$	
	R_1	R_2	R_2	R_1	R_1	R_2
I_a	H	H	III_a	H	IV_a	H
I_b	H	5- CH_3	III_b	5- CH_3	IV_b	5- CH_3
I_c	H	5-Cl	III_c	5-Cl	IV_c	5-Cl
I_d	H	5-Br	III_d	5-Br	IV_d	5-Br
I_e	H	4- CH_3	III_e	6- CH_3	IV_e	4- CH_3
I_f	H	3- CH_3	III_f	7- CH_3	IV_f	3- CH_3

$II_{(a-f)} = I_{(a-f)}$, where $R_1 = Br$; $V_{(a-f)} = IV_{(a-f)}$, where $R_1 = Br$.

The esters $I_{(a-f)}$ ^{1,3} were first brominated to the ω -bromoesters by means of cupric bromide in anhydrous dioxan, a reagent which selectively brominates a side chain^{10,11}. In the majority of the cases the brominated products were produced in excellent yield. On subjecting the ω -bromoesters $II_{(a-f)}$ to Baker-Venkataraman transformation by potassium hydroxide in dry dioxan, the desired 2-benzofuroylcoumaran-3-ones $III_{(a-f)}$ were directly obtained, obviously through the intermediates $V_{(a-f)}$, which were not isolated. The formation of the postulated intermediates find support from the works of Wheeler *et al.*^{8,12} in connection with the mechanism of Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement.

not improve the melting point apparently indicating some degree of cyclisation during recrystallisation. The chloroform solutions containing the bromo compounds were, therefore, directly refluxed to produce the corresponding coumaran-3-ones $III_{(a-f)}$. The yields, however, were not as good as obtainable by the first method.

All the coumaran-3-ones obtained by two methods were identical and 11 gave positive ferric reaction. Their elemental analysis and i.r. data agreed well with expected values. (OH at 3420-50 cm^{-1} , and 1:3 diketone group at 1540-1640 cm^{-1})¹⁴.

Experimental

Melting points, determined in open capillaries are uncorrected. The i.r. spectra were recorded in Beckman infrared spectrometer Model DK-2A.

2-(2'-Benzofuroxy)-w-bromo acetophenones :— Finely powdered copper(II) bromide (0.02 mole) was added to anhydrous dioxan (60 ml) and refluxed for 30 min with exclusion of moisture. After cooling the 2-(2'-benzofuroxy) acetophenone (0.01 mole) was added to the mixture and refluxing was continued for 2½ hrs. A grey white precipitate collected at the bottom of the flask showing the formation of copper(I) bromide. After cooling copper(I) bromide was filtered off at the pump. Dioxan was partially removed under reduced pressure, and the filtrate was diluted with water. The products when viscous were extracted with benzene, washed and dried (MgSO₄). The residue left after removal of the solvent was recrystallized from suitable solvent. The names, yields, colours, m.ps. and solvents of recrystallisation are given below :

Ia. 2-(2'-Benzofuroxy)-w-bromoacetophenone, 81%, m.p. 128-29° (Methanol). (Found : C, 56.5 ; H, 3.0 ; C₁₇H₁₁O₄Br requires C, 56.8 ; H, 3.1%).

Ib. 5-Methyl-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)-w-bromoacetophenone, 49%, brownish yellow, m.p. 135-36° (Ethanol), (Found : C, 57.6 ; H, 3.4 ; C₁₈H₁₃O₄Br requires C, 57.9 ; H, 3.5%).

Ic. 5-Chloro-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)-w-bromoacetophenone, 80%, light yellow, m.p. 145-46° (Ethanol). (Found : C, 51.4 ; H, 2.6 ; C₁₇H₁₀O₄BrCl requires C, 51.8 ; H, 2.5%).

IId. 5-Bromo-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)-w-bromoacetophenone, 80%, light brown, m.p. 139-41°, (Ethanol) (Found : C, 46.4 ; H, 2.0 ; C₁₇H₁₀O₄Br₂ requires C, 46.6 ; H, 2.3%)

Ie. 4-Methyl-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)-w-bromoacetophenone, 33%, brownish yellow, m.p. 121-22° (Ethanol). (Found : C, 58.2, H, 3.3 ; C₁₈H₁₃O₄Br requires C, 57.9 ; H, 3.5%).

IIf. 3-Methyl-2-(2'-benzofuroxy)-w-bromoacetophenone, gummy mass.

Coumaran-3-ones III (a-t) :

First Method (General Procedure)

The mixture of a w-bromoacetophenone, II (a-t), anhydrous dioxan (20 ml) and potassium hydroxide (a little more than one mole per mole of ester) was gently refluxed for ½ hr. A yellow solid separated during heating. It was then cooled and treated with excess of dilute sulphuric acid. The solid which separated was filtered, washed, dried

and recrystallised from ethanol. The names, yields, colours and m.ps. are given below :—

IIIa. 2-(2'-Benzofuroyl)coumaran-3-one, 98%, reddish brown, m.p. 157-58°.

IIIb. 5-Methyl-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)coumaran-3-one, 90% orange yellow, m.p. 172-73°.

IIIc. 5-Chloro-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)coumaran-3-one, 70% yellow, m.p. 150-52°.

IIId. 5-Bromo-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)coumaran-3-one, 90%, yellow, m.p. 174-75°.

IIIe. 6-Methyl-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)coumaran-3-one, 83%. brownish yellow, m.p. 161-62°.

IIIIf. 7-Methyl-2-(2'-benzofuroyl)coumaran-3-one, 15% (of the acetophenone) brownish yellow, m.p. 164-65°.

Second Method (General Procedure) :—

To the solution of a 1 : 3 diketone (IV_{a-t}) in dry chloroform containing anhydrous potassium carbonate, molar proportion of bromine in dry chloroform was slowly added at 0° with stirring, till the colour due to bromine disappeared. The solution was next refluxed for 1 hr. cooled and filtered. The solid was boiled with water and the hot filtrate on cooling and acidification deposited crystals of the coumaran-3-one which were collected and recrystallised.

Repeated extraction of the chloroform filtrate with sodium carbonate (5%) and acidification of the alkaline extract gave an additional amount of the product although in small amounts.

The yields calculated on the basis of the diketone taken are given below :

IIIa	33.5%	IIIb	15.5%	IIIc	23.5%
IIId	61%	IIIe	37%	IIIf	20%

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